

**SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS ON STEROLS, BILE ACID, HORMONE,
ETC. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF 7-METHYL-0:3:3-BICYCLO-
OCTANNE-1-ONE-3-CARBOXYLIC ACID**

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A synthesis of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one-3-carboxylic acid has been described. By the oxidation of the above ketonic acid, the locking of the fused carbon rings has been shown to be *cis*.

Wieland and Schlichting (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 276) obtained through the oxidative degradation of desoxycholic acid, a tetracarboxylic acid $C_{14}H_{24}O_8$, which on pyrolysis gave rise to a keto-dicarboxylic acid of the composition $C_{11}H_{20}O_4$ to which they assigned the structure (I, R = C_2H_5 , CO_2H). As a preliminary to the synthesis of the above pyroketo-acid, we have synthesised the simpler keto-acid (I, R = H).

Ethyl 2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentylcyanoacetate (II, R = H) has been prepared by the reduction of ethyl 2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentylidene-cyanoacetate (Linstead and Errington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 666; *cf.* Banerjee, *Science & Culture*, 1944, 9, 456) with aluminium amalgam in an ethereal solution. The yield of the above reduction, however, could be considerably improved upon that obtained by Linstead *et al* (*loc. cit.*) either by submitting the aluminium sludge, after filtration, to extraction with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus or by treating the reaction mixture with ice-cold dilute mineral acid and then extraction with solvent. Potassio salt of (II, R = H) is condensed with ethyl bromoacetate in an alcoholic solution, when diethyl α -cyano- α -(2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentyl)succinate (II, R = CH_2 , CO_2Et) is obtained, which on hydrolysis yields 2-methyl-2-carboxycyclopentylsuccinic acid (III, R = H). The triethyl ester (III, R = Et) smoothly undergoes Dieckmann's condensation to afford ethyl 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (IV) which gives an intense ferric chloride coloration in an alcoholic solution. 7-Methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one-3-carboxylic acid is obtained by the hydrolysis of the β -ketonic ester as a viscous oil. The keto-acid (I, R = H) on oxidation with concentrated nitric acid yields a solid acid, which after several crystallisations from acidulated water melts at $124-26^\circ$. Mixed melting point with an authentic sample of *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 611; Bachmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1261) shows no depression (melting point of the above *cis* acid was found to depend considerably on the rate of heating). The formation of the *cis*-locking in this case is in conformity with our previous observation in the preparation of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one (Banerjee, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-Methylcarbethoxycyclopentylidene-cyanoacetate.—Previously Linstead and

Errington (*loc. cit.*) prepared this compound from ethyl 2-methylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate and ethyl cyanoacetate under 4000 atm. pressure in 20% yield. Utilising the modified method of Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452), we obtained the condensation product in much improved yield.

Ethyl cyanoacetate (21 g.), ethyl 2-methylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (32 g.), ammonium acetate (10 g.), glacial acetic acid (12 c. c.) and dry benzene (50 c. c.) were refluxed in a 500 c. c. flask, to which a water separator (Cope *et al. loc. cit.*) had been attached, until no further water separated. Further ammonium acetate (5 g.) and acetic acid (10 c. c.) were added and again refluxed for 8 hours, when very little water was found to separate. Reaction mixture was then transferred to a separating funnel with benzene and repeatedly washed with water. Benzene was removed and the residue fractionated when 32.3 g. of the condensation product boiling $150^{\circ}/4$ mm. were obtained together with a forerun of unchanged materials.

Ethyl 2-Methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentylcyanoacetate.—Aluminium amalgam (32 g.) was covered with an ethereal solution (500 c.c.) of the above unsaturated cyano-ester and left at the room temperature for 7 days with frequent addition of a small quantity of water. Aluminium sludge was filtered off and was extracted with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus. Ethereal solutions were combined and the solvent was removed. The residue boiled at $138^{\circ}/3.5$ mm. and the yield was 31 g. Similar yield was also obtained when the ethereal solution together with the sludge was poured into an ice-cold dilute mineral acid and well shaken until the mixture considerably cleared up, then the ether layer was separated and the aqueous layer was re-extracted with ether and the combined ethereal solution was worked up in the usual manner.

Diethyl α -Cyano- α -(2-methyl-2-carbethoxypentyl)-succinate.—Potassium (2.3 g.) pulverised under dry toluene (30 c.c.) was treated in an ice-bath with absolute alcohol (12 c.c.) added dropwise and left overnight. Ethyl 2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentylcyanoacetate (15.6 g.) was slowly added to it with cooling and the mixture allowed to stand for 1½ hours. Ethyl bromoacetate (7 c.c.) was next added to the potassio-salt thus formed, when potassium bromide separated out in the cold. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 4 hours, followed by refluxing for 8 hours. Water was added to it after cooling and the product after addition of some ether was twice washed with water, and dried. Solvents were removed and the residue was distilled in vacuum, when about 20 g. of the condensation product were obtained, b.p. $207^{\circ}/7-8$ mm. (Found: C, 61.5; H 7.4. $C_{11}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 61.2; H, 7.6 per cent).

2-Methyl-2-carboxycyclopentylsuccinic Acid.—Diethyl α -cyano- α -(2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentyl)-succinate (18 g.) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (110 c.c.) for 50 hours, when white crystals were found to separate out in the cold. Crystals were filtered off and recrystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m.p. $208-11^{\circ}$ with previous shrinking at 200° . (Found: C, 53.82; H, 6.67. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 54.1; H, 6.6 per cent).

Diethyl 2-Methyl-2-carbethoxycyclopentylsuccinate.—The filtered hydrochloric acid solution obtained above was completely evaporated to dryness on a water-bath in a basin. The crude acid together with ammonium chloride was esterified by refluxing with alcohol (50 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 7c.c.) for 36 hours. Ice-cold water

was added to it and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, ice-cold caustic potash solution and then again with water, and dried. Ether was removed and the residue on distillation boiled at $170^{\circ}/5$ mm. The alkaline washing was acidified in the cold and the separated oil was extracted with ether, the solvent was removed and the residue, after being dried in vacuum, was re-esterified by the alcohol-sulphuric acid method. It was worked up in the usual way bringing the total yield of the tri-ester to 12 g. (Found: C, 62.10; H, 8.36. $C_{17}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 62.19; H, 8.53 per cent).

Ethyl 7-Methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate.—Triethyl ester (III, R = Et; 10.4 g.) was refluxed with sodium dust (1.5 g.) in dry benzene for 3 hours, when whole of the metallic sodium disappeared. Ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid was poured into the cooled reaction mixture. Benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. Combined ether-benzene solution was successively washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and water. Solvents were removed. On distillation in vacuum the product boiled at $168^{\circ}/9$ mm., yield 6.5 g. (Found: C, 64.15; H, 7.86. $C_{17}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 63.63; H, 7.8 per cent).

7-Methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid.—Ethyl 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (6 g.) was refluxed with 20% sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) for 16 hours. The cooled acid solution was thoroughly extracted with ether and the residue left after evaporation of the solvent boiled at $162-165^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 3 g. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 7.9. $C_{16}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 65.9; H, 7.7 per cent).

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way after purification by means of crystallisation, melted at 234° . (Found: C, 54.9; H, 6.92. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2$ requires C, 55.2; H, 7.1 per cent).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (I; R = H).—7-Methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (1.8 g.) was heated with nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 14 c.c.) on a boiling water-bath for 1 hour. It was then refluxed with an addition of water for further 1 hour. The solution was evaporated as much as possible on a water-bath and then left in an evacuated desiccator on caustic potash, when the product crystallised out. Adhering gum was removed on a porous plate and the product was crystallised several times from dilute hydrochloric acid, when it melted at $124-26^{\circ}$. The m.p. was not depressed on an admixture of *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid. (Found: C, 56.0; H, 7.0. $C_8H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.99 per cent).

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